

Research project: To See the Tree and the Forest.

March 6, 2023

FCT Exploratory Research Project (2022.08122.PTDC)

To See the Tree and the Forest

Reading the Poetry of

António Ramos Rosa

from a Distance

01-03-2023 > 31-08-2024

FCT Project Started

Between March 2023 and August 2024, the Institute for Comparative Literature (<https://ilcml.com/en/>) will develop the research project **To See the Tree and the Forest. Reading the Poetry of António Ramos Rosa from a Distance** (2022.08122.PTDC). This exploratory project was funded by FCT – Foundation for Science and Technology under the 2022 Call for R&D Projects in all Scientific Domains.

Drawing on techniques from Computational Literary Studies and Digital Humanities, the project aims to apply computational methods of text analysis to the complete works of António Ramos Rosa. In particular, the project team will investigate how entities such as plants, animals, and minerals are part of a poetic construct that conceives the world from an ecological perspective. In

this regard, one of the goals is to reread Ramos Rosa's poetry and understand how it contributes to imagining a more inclusive planetary coexistence between humans and more-than-humans. This Digital Environmental Humanities project is thus linked to recent research paradigms in ecocriticism, post-humanism, and new materialisms. In addition to our core framework, the project will comprise two components dedicated to digital aesthetics and electronic literature. These components will include the design of artifacts of information visualization and a curated exhibition of digital literary works based on the project's datasets.

The research team members are Bruno Ministro (<https://ilcml.com/en/membros/bruno-ministro-en/>) (Principal Investigator, ILCML), Ana Paula Coutinho (<https://ilcml.com/en/membros/ana-paula-coutinho-en/>) (Co-Principal Investigator, ILCML), João Paulo Guimarães (<https://ilcml.com/en/membros/joao-paulo-guimaraes-en/>) (ILCML), Paulo Silva Pereira (CLP – University of Coimbra), and Helena Costa Carvalho (CLEPUL – University of Lisbon). The consultants are Manuel Portela (CLP – U. Coimbra) and Martin Paul Eve (Birkbeck, University of London). The project is hosted by the Faculty of Arts and Humanities of the University of Porto, and the Institute for Comparative Literature (<https://ilcml.com/en/>) serves as the hosting R&D unit.

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